

Oslo, 14.06.2024

Dear Dr Olwenn Martin,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of the manuscript “Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with those used in systematic review: research protocol” after a second round of peer review. We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback and are grateful for the comments and suggestions for improvement of our manuscript.

We have responded to each comment individually, and the suggested revisions are shown with blue text in the tables below. Table 1 contain an overview of our point-by-point response to all comments and the revisions provided (with line numbers for the revised text in the clean version of the revised manuscript).

We look forward to hearing from you regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

Camilla Svendsen

Table 1. Response to the referee comments.

Comment number	Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Report, reviewer comments	Author response
General comments		
1	I very much like the new, sleeker methods.	So do we!
Remaining issues that could materially impact the scientific quality of the planned research		
2	I am pleased to read that discussions will be supported by an experienced and neutral moderator. I remain disappointed that reliable methods for consensus development (rather than only voting) are not clearly explained in the paper especially as there is a mature literature to draw on.	We appreciate the maturity of the literature but it is not feasible in the present manuscript to do it justice. We would also emphasise that our consensus method is not “only voting” - the voting step is to (a) validate the consensus achieved through the discussion process, and (b) allow people not able to participate in live discussion to contribute through an asynchronous process. This is a process we are familiar with using ourselves and feel we can apply successfully. We also noticed that we removed reference to the consensus protocols on which our approach is based (the SEVCO and GRADE Ontologies) and have added these back in lines 169-170.
3	Lines 155-156: other sources might be used... will you search? Brainstorm among members? Clarification would be helpful	We have added clarification on how we will identify other sources if needed. On lines 158-159, we have added: “ which will be identified by an Internet search or brainstorming within the PG and SAG. ”
Other remaining issues with the planned methods		

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4	<p>We understand that the ethics of collecting race or ethnicity information about study participants are interpreted differently in different countries. You should explain the rules regarding collecting such information in the institution applying for ethical clearance in the manuscript to justify this omission.</p>	<p>An explanation on why we will not be collecting information on race or ethnicity have now been added on lines 184-187: “Information on race or ethnicity will not be collected because in Norway this information falls under the category of “sensitive personal data” and on a general note this type of data is not legal to be collected or handled.”</p>
5	<p>The clarification offered as response to reviewers’ comments is welcome. For transparency on this aspect of the methods, the content of the following paragraph ought to be added to the manuscript “The use of an experienced and neutral moderator should reduce the potential for some persons to dominate the discussion. Voting online after the event should also allow for more ease at disagreeing with ‘strong personalities/ assumed higher in the hierarchical system. Also, we are planning for a diverse mix of experiences and backgrounds in the group. The plan is for the discussions to be facilitated by an experienced moderator (PW) who will be aware of the need to ensure dominant personalities do not overwhelm the discussion. The key element of the method is the asynchronous anonymous comment and voting. Because we are aiming at near-full consensus, this will give all participants the opportunity to contribute, with the requirement that their comments are taken into account. If the participants feel their comments are not responded to,</p>	<p>We have added a paragraph in the “Chapter 4 Limitations” to address this, lines 229-237: “For the online group discussions in Phase 3, there is a risk for some persons to dominate the discussion. To reduce this, an experienced and neutral moderator (PW) will facilitate the discussions. Anonymous voting online should also allow for more ease at disagreeing with strong personalities and participants assumed to higher in a social hierarchy. Because we are aiming at a high level of consensus, voting will give all participants the opportunity to contribute over several rounds of development of the cross-walk, with the requirement that their comments are considered in each round of discussion. If any participants feel their comments are not responded to, they can vote “no” in the next round of voting. Also, we are planning for a diverse mix of experiences and backgrounds in the group.”</p>

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	they can vote “no” in the next round of voting.” Followed by a brief statement regarding the limitations of the proposed approach. The citation provided in the response should also be included in the paper itself.	We have also reintroduced citation of the SEVCO and GRADE ontology development protocols as references for our consensus method, around line 170.
6	Lines 124-128: New information, “the TF-IDF” method was “not successful” – maybe say why so other people can understand for future projects of a similar nature.	This was due to the method being relatively inefficient compared to manual identification of terms. We have added explanation of this on lines 128-130: “.....and it was found to be less efficient than expected, with challenges on corpus selection, data cleaning, and optimisation of term abstraction and rank ordering. We have therefore determined that manual identification of terms will be done instead.”
7	The GRADE ontology mentioned by the authors in their response is not explained or cited in the manuscript.	We have reintroduced citation of the SEVCO and GRADE ontology development protocols as references for our consensus method, lines 169-170: “The approach is adapted from the consensus process used in the development of the SEVCO methods ontology and the GRADE Ontology.”
Other questions and comments about the protocol		
8	The abstract needs to be updated that CRA and SR definitions aren’t authoritative. It’s updated in lines 50-66,	The cover page is in the system and we were not able to update the abstract on there. We will make another attempt.

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	but the one on the cover page (in the system?) has not been, if that matters.	
9	Reviewer 4, 4.1 Line 228-229. Pg 12 of review. Networks of members in the groups for recruitment – I still think it's important. Only recruiting people you know will not result in a diverse group. I am glad to see the text included in S-8.	We are happy to hear that you like the text that has been added.
10	“Is table S-1 a duplicate of table 1 (now table 2)” The clarification is helpful but I think it would be good to add that information in the caption for Table 2 (more detailed steps available in S-1).	Both Table 2 and Table S-1 shows steps in the cross-mapping, however Table 2, which is included in the manuscript only displays the main steps, whereas Table S-1 shows all the steps and more details. This is explained in the main text (lines 165-167): “The main steps in the cross-mapping are shown in Table 2. A more detailed overview of the steps is included in the Supplementary materials (Table S-1).” However, to avoid confusion, we have now also included in the table description of Table S-1: “ This overview is a detailed version of Table 2. ”
11.	The authors have made clear that their inspection of the core terminology will be limited to systematic reviews that include quantitative health outcomes, I can see that they are making a fair comparison. However, line 103 states that ‘For CRAs, the scope is limited to methods for quantitative systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence synthesis.’ My understanding is that for both CRAs and	<p>We have added “and SRs” in line 103 and the sentence is now: “For CRAs and SRs, the scope is limited to methods for quantitative systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence synthesis.”</p> <p>We have not changed the title, as we feel it is OK for a manuscript to have a narrower focus than</p>

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	<p>systematic reviews 'the scope is limited to methods for quantitative systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence synthesis.' I would like to see this same clarity reflected in the title. Without amending the title the asymmetry in scope remains as systematic reviews can include qualitative research, which is not of interest here.</p>	<p>may be implied in a title that is necessarily a very short summary of the content of the paper, so long as the manuscript is consistent with the title.</p>